

Phage Display as a Tool to Discover BBB-Shuttle Peptides: Panning Against a Human Blood-Brain Barrier Cellular Model

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ABSTRACT:

Most potential drugs for the treatment of CNS disorders do not cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB). Much research effort has been devoted to the discovery of new BBB-shuttle peptides – most of which have been identified by phage display. Here we report for the first time on the use of phage display against a human BBB cellular model which mimics the characteristics of the BBB. From the panning experiment of a 12-mer library, the SGVYKVAYDWQH (SGV) peptide sequence was selected and its permeability validated in the aforementioned model. Furthermore, internalisation studies suggested that SGV internalises through a clathrin-mediated mechanism and that it increases the uptake of a cargo in endothelial cells. These results highlight the usefulness of *in vitro* BBB models for the discovery of BBB-shuttle peptides through phage display libraries.

Keywords: blood-brain barrier; phage display; blood-brain barrier cellular model; BBB-shuttle peptides

INTRODUCTION

Blood-Brain Barrier

The blood-brain barrier (BBB) separates circulating blood from extracellular brain fluid and regulates transport to the central nervous system (CNS). This transport is rigorously controlled by the tight junctions between the endothelial cells that form the barrier.^{1,2} These junctions hamper brain entry of most potential therapeutic molecules used to treat CNS disorders such as brain cancer, Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease. Indeed, more than 98% of low molecular weight candidate drugs and almost 100% of large therapeutic candidate drugs cannot cross the BBB.³

One way to circumvent this hurdle is to use BBB-shuttles – entities that have the capacity to carry a cargo across the BBB through either active or passive transport.^{4,5} In this way, a wide range of therapeutic molecules can reach the brain through binding, either covalently or not, to a BBB-shuttle. Endogenous proteins,⁶ peptides⁷ and antibodies⁸ have been used as BBB-shuttles. Peptides have several advantages over other molecules. In this regard, they have low immunogenicity and production costs and are amenable to chemical synthesis. In recent decades, several peptides have been reported to cross the BBB and transport cargoes into the brain.⁷ The sources of these peptides are diverse, ranging from the mimicry of endogenous proteins to the use of phage display. The latter technique has been applied both *in vivo* and *in vitro* on immobilised receptors and isolated cell lines, but not in a BBB cellular model to date.

A strategy widely used to find BBB-shuttles is to start from neurotropic proteins and identify the moiety responsible for transport through sequence alignment, screening of synthesised overlapping fragments, or structural studies involving X-ray and NMR.⁹ These approaches allow the identification of peptides that cross the BBB by an active mechanism. Angiopep-2 (TFFYGGSRGKRNNFKTEEY), one of the first peptides reported and one of those most advanced in clinical trials, was identified from sequence alignment of aprotinin with other human proteins with a Kunitz domain.^{10,11} A small library was generated and its transport was evaluated using an *in vitro* BBB model and *in situ* brain perfusion. The results indicated that Angiopep-2 has a higher capacity to accumulate in the brain than other proteins. Furthermore, this peptide has been conjugated to a multitude of cargoes, such as dendrimers.¹² ApoE ((LRKLRKRL)₂), a peptide derived from apolipoproteinE, also shows high efficiency in transporting other proteins into

the CNS.¹³ In this case, several sequences of the protein were expressed as fusion proteins with a lysosomal enzyme after transient hepatic expression in mice, and their capacity to direct this enzyme to the brain was proven.

In both cases, extensive knowledge of the BBB, its receptors, and structure was required. A promising alternative is to use unbiased libraries of peptides as the starting population of molecules and screen for those structures with high transport capacity. Several methods can be used to obtain libraries of peptides, including one-bead-one-compound^{14,15} and phage display.¹⁶

Phage Display in the Discovery of BBB-Shuttle Peptides

Phage display was introduced by G.P. Smith in 1985 and has become one of the most popular techniques for screening peptides against a given target.^{16,17,18} A phage can be engineered to accommodate segments of foreign DNA, which will be expressed as a fusion protein with one of the coat proteins of the phage. The strength of this technique lies in the generation of an enormous diversity of exogenous peptides or proteins displayed on the surface of the phage using standard yet rapid molecular biology methods.

The most commonly used vectors for phage display are fd and M13. These express filamentous bacteriophages that infect F plasmid-containing gram-negative bacteria, such as *E. coli*. Also, two types of coat protein are used for phage display, namely pIII, which can display 3-5 copies of the foreign sequence, and pVIII, which can display about 2700 copies. However, most phage display libraries use the former as it tends to produce binders with higher affinities.

A typical biopanning experiment has the following five main steps: incubation of the phage library with the target; washing of the unbound phage; recovery of the bound phage; amplification of the recovered phage through infecting the bacterial host; and plating of the retrieved phage to isolate plaques for DNA sequencing. This process is repeated with higher stringency by incubating the suspension of recovered phage with the target, usually 2 to 4 times. This procedure leads to the enrichment of a small number of peptide motifs with specific binding affinity for the target. In the context of BBB-shuttle discovery, these panning experiments, which cover a variety of techniques, have been performed *in vitro* on isolated cell lines and immobilised receptors and *in vivo* (Table I).

The most straightforward experiment involves panning against an immobilised receptor that is relevant for the transport of molecules in the BBB. For instance, a 12-mer peptide library was panned against immobilised GM1 as target. The G23 sequence, when coupled to polymeric vesicles, was observed to mediate transport across the BBB both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.¹⁹ Other examples are peptide B6, which was found by panning for motifs that bind to hTfR,²⁰ and peptide-22, where the panning was directed to the extracellular domain of human low density lipoprotein receptor (LDLR).²¹

Moreover, *in vivo* phage display has been reported to provide phage-displayed peptides able to cross the BBB from systemic circulation.^{22,23} In these experiments, the phage library is injected into mice and left to circulate for 24 h to minimise the presence of high background phage in the circulation. The brain is then removed, the phage are recovered, and the DNA sequences obtained. For example, an *in vivo* screening of a 12-mer phage library was shown to yield a peptide specific to the brain, called TGN. Nanoparticles displaying TGN exhibit significantly higher efficiency in brain transport when compared with native phage.²⁴ Similar examples are the discovery of CRT²⁵ and PepC7.²⁶ The phage library can also be perfused in mice to enrich for peptides recognising brain endothelial cells. This approach was used in the discovery of GLA and GYR peptides from a 15-mer peptide library.²⁷ In another example, a family of peptides homing to the brain was discovered by intravascular administration of a cyclic 7-mer library to rats.²⁸

However, *in vivo* models are technically challenging, skill-demanding, and time-consuming and they also require higher amounts of compounds. In contrast, panning against isolated cell lines is easier to handle and has a greater throughput capacity and a lower cost. A relevant example is the discovery of THR and HAI peptides, which were found by selection on chicken embryo fibroblast cells expressing hTfR (CEF + hTfR).²⁹

BBB Cellular Model

Isolated cell lines cannot mimic all the characteristics of the BBB, therefore cell-based BBB models were developed to cover the gap between cultured cells and *in vivo* models. *In vitro* BBB models are relatively high-throughput and are suitable for optimising BBB permeability. A range of *in vitro* cellular BBB models have been developed that can incorporate cells of non-cerebral origin or cerebral endothelial cells from primary

cultures. These cells can be configured as monocultures, co-cultures or triple co-cultures with other cells of the neurovascular unit.³⁰

A BBB cellular model recently developed in Prof. Cecchelli's laboratory has shown good correlation with human clinical data.³¹ This model consists of a co-culture of human brain capillary endothelial cells derived from pluripotent stem cells and bovine pericytes on semi-permeable membranes of a transwell. Under highly specific culture conditions, the endothelial cells of this model show tight junctions between them, become polarised, have proteolytic activity, and express efflux pumps, thus resembling the BBB as a whole. Once the endothelial cells are differentiated, these are placed in new wells, without the pericytes, to perform the assay. This BBB model was used in the validation of several BBB-shuttles, such as THRre³² and MiniAp-4.³³

In order to identify peptide sequences that translocate across the BBB, here we used the *in vitro* human BBB model to screen a phage library containing random 12-amino acid sequences. The aim of this paper is to present this method as a new tool through which to identify BBB-shuttles and the first evidence that the peptides obtained using this approach are promising hits for BBB-peptide shuttles.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The Ph.D.-12 Phage Display Peptide Library, *E. coli* ER2738 host strain and the -96 gIII sequencing primer 5'd(CCCTCATAGTTAGCGTAACG) were supplied by New England Biolabs, Inc. (Ipswich, MA). Xgal (5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl- β -D-galactopyranoside) and IPTG (isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactopyranoside) were from American Bioanalytical, Inc. (Natick, MA). Protected amino acids were supplied by Iris Biotech (Marktredwitz, Germany). XTT cell proliferation kit was purchased from Biological Industries (Cromwell, CT). ChemMatrix resin was purchased from PCAS BioMatrix (QC, Canada). Diisopropylethylamine (DIEA), *N,N'*-diisopropylcarbodiimide (DIC) and ninhydrin were supplied by Fluka Chemika (Buchs, Switzerland). Solvents for peptide synthesis and liquid chromatography were supplied by SDS (Barcelona, Spain). Trifluoroacetic acid was purchased from Scharlau (Barcelona, Spain). Other chemicals

used were obtained from Aldrich (Milwaukee, WI) and were of the highest purity commercially available.

Phage Display

All methodologies for the use of the phage display libraries, including preparation of the media and solutions, ER2738 strain maintenance, phage amplification and titering, and purification of single-stranded M13 viral DNA, was performed as described in the Ph.D.TM Phage Display Libraries Instructions Manual, with some modifications.

Media and Solutions

IPTG/Xgal stock solution: 1.25 g IPTG and 1 g Xgal in 25 mL DMF. Tetracycline stock suspension: 20 mg/mL tetracycline in 1:1 ethanol:water. LB/IPTG/Xgal plates: 1L LB medium, 15 g/l agar and 1 mL IPTG/Xgal stock solution. LB/Tet plates: 1L LB medium, 15 g/L agar and 1 mL tetracycline stock suspension. PEG/NaCl: 20% (w/v) PEG, 2.5 M NaCl. Iodide buffer: 10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0), 1 mM EDTA and 4 M NaI.

Strain Maintenance

ER2738 host strain (F' *proA*⁺*B*⁺ *lacI*^q Δ (*lacZ*)*M15* *zzf::Tn10(Tet^R)*/*fhuA2 glnV* Δ (*lac-proAB*) *thi-1* Δ (*hsdS-mcrB*)5) was plated onto tetracycline-containing plates (LB/Tet plates) and incubated at 37°C overnight and stored at 4°C in the dark for up to 1 month.

Phage Titering

10 to 10³-fold serial dilutions of phage were prepared in LB: 10⁸-10¹¹ for amplified phage culture supernatants and 10¹-10⁴ for unamplified panning eluates. 10 μ l of each phage dilution was added to 200 μ l of mid-log phase (OD₆₀₀ ~ 0.5) of ER2738 and then vortexed and incubated for 5 min. The infected phage was transferred to LB/IPTG/Xgal plates. The plates were incubated overnight at 37°C, and the plaques were counted to obtain the titer in plaque forming units (pfu):

plaque forming units (pfu) = (number of plaques · dilution factor)/10 (μl)

Phage Amplification

The phage recovered from the acceptor compartment was amplified by adding 200 μl of the phage to 20 ml of mid-log phase ($OD_{600} \sim 0.5$) of ER2738 and then vortexed and incubated for 4 h at 37°C with vigorous shaking. Next, the culture was transferred to a centrifuge tube and spun for 15 min at 5000 rpm at 4°C. The upper 80% of the supernatant was transferred to a fresh centrifuge tube and 24 ml of 20% PEG/2.5 M NaCl was added. The phage was allowed to precipitate overnight at 4°C. The following day, the phage was precipitated by spinning for 25 min at 5000 rpm at 4°C. The supernatant was discarded and the pellet was re-suspended in 1 mL of PBS and transferred to a new micro-centrifuge tube. The residual cells were discarded by spinning for 5 min at 14000 rpm at 4°C, and the supernatant was recovered in a new tube. A second precipitation was performed with 0.5 ml of 20% PEG/2.5 M NaCl for 1 h in ice. Finally, the phage was recovered by spinning for 15 min at 14,000 rpm at 4°C. The supernatant was then discarded, and the pellet was dissolved in 200 μl of PBS.

Purification of Single-Stranded M13 Viral DNA for Sequencing

ER2738 was infected with the selected phage colony, which was picked from the titration plates, and the phage was amplified following the procedure described before. In the final step, the phage was suspended in 100 μl of iodide buffer by vigorously tapping the tube. 250 μl of ethanol was added and incubated for 20 min at room temperature. The single-stranded phage DNA was recovered by spinning for 10 min at 14,000 rpm at 4°C, and the supernatant was discarded. The pellet was washed with 0.5 mL of 70% cold ethanol and re-spinned, and the supernatant was discarded. The pellet was briefly dried under vacuum and suspended in 30 μl of DI H₂O. The peptide-encoding nucleotide sequences were determined with the -96 gIII sequencing primer 5'd(CCCTCATAGTTAGCGTAACG) included in Ph.D.-12™ Phage Display Peptide Library.

Panning in the Human BBB Cellular Model

The human BBB cellular model was prepared, and the assay was performed as described in the following section. A 100-fold dilution of the initial Ph.D.-12™ Phage Display Peptide Library was used as the initial phage pool: 5 µl of phage and 10.5 µl of Lucifer Yellow (1 mg/mL) in 500 µl of Ringer HEPES. After the 2 h assay, the phage was recovered from the donor and acceptor compartment, and 200 µl from the acceptor compartment was amplified as described before. 10 µl of the amplified phage was diluted in 500 µl of Ringer HEPES and used in the second round of panning. After the final round, the phage was recovered and titered. Around 31-34 bacteriophage clones from the last round were randomly picked out and subjected to DNA sequencing.

Human BBB Cellular Model Assay

These experiments were performed using the model developed in Prof. R. Cecchelli's laboratory.³¹ In brief, the endothelial cells and the pericytes were defrosted in gelatin-coated Petri dishes (Corning). The endothelial cells were cultured in supplemented endothelial cell growth medium (Sciencells) and the pericytes in DMEM pH 6.8. After 48 h, endothelial cells were seeded in 12-well Transwell inserts (8000 cell/well) and pericytes were plated in 12-well plates (50000 cells/well) previously coated with Matrigel and gelatin, respectively. The medium was changed every 2-3 days and the assays were performed 7-8 days after seeding.

The following concentrations of compounds were used: $5 \cdot 10^{10}$ pfu as the initial pool in the phage display experiment and 50 µM for the SGV peptide. Lucifer Yellow (50 µM) was added as a control of barrier integrity. To perform the assay, 500 µl of the compound in Ringer HEPES was added to the donor compartment and 1500 µl of Ringer HEPES was introduced into the acceptor compartment. The samples were evaluated in triplicates. The plates were incubated for 2 h at 37°C, and the solutions from both compartments were recovered and analysed. The phage was amplified and the DNA sequenced, and the amount of peptide was quantified using UPLC quantification.

Apparent permeability:

$$P_{app} = (Q_A(t) \cdot V_D) / (t \cdot A \cdot Q_D(t_0))$$

where P_{app} is obtained in cm/s, $Q_A(t)$ is the amount of compound at the time t in the acceptor well, V_D is the volume in the donor well, t is time in seconds, A is the area of the

membrane in cm and $Q_D(t_0)$ is the amount of compound in the donor compartment at the beginning of the experiment.

Peptide Synthesis and Chromatography

Peptides were assembled using Fmoc/*t*Bu solid-phase peptide synthesis in an automatic peptide synthesiser (Liberty Blue synthesiser, CEM). The peptides were synthesised in a 250- μ mol scale on Rink Amide ChemMatrix resin using L-amino acids. Between the coupling and deprotection step, 3 washes with 5 mL of DMF for 30 s were performed.

Initial Conditioning of the Resin

Rink Amide ChemMatrix[®] resin with a substitution of 0.49 mmol/g was conditioned by washing with MeOH (5 x 30 s), DMF (5 x 30 s), DCM (5 x 30 s), and 1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) in DCM (2 x 10 min), followed by DCM (5 x 30 s), DMF (5 x 30 s), DCM (5 x 30 s). Then washing with 5% DIEA in DCM (2 x 30 s), and finally with DCM (5 x 30 s) and DMF (5 x 30 s).

Identification Test

The Kaiser colorimetric³⁴ test assay was used to detect primary amines bound to solid phase.

Fmoc Group Removal

The Fmoc group was removed by treating the resin with 10% (w/v) piperazine in 90:10 (NMP/EtOH) + 0.1 M HOBt (1:05 min, 90°C). The resin was then washed with DMF (3 x 30 s).

Coupling Methods

For the synthesis of the peptides, the following L-amino acids were used: Fmoc-Ala-OH, Fmoc-Asp(*O**t*Bu)-OH, Fmoc-Glu(*t*Bu)-OH, Fmoc-Gly-OH, Fmoc-His(Trt)-OH, Fmoc-

Lys(Boc)-OH, Fmoc-Ser(*t*Bu)-OH, Fmoc-Trp(Boc)-OH, Fmoc-Tyr(*t*Bu)-OH, and Fmoc-Val-OH.

The protected amino acids (0.2M in DMF), *N,N'*-diisopropylcarbodiimide (DIC) (0.5 M in DMF), Oxyma (1M in DMF), and HOBt (1M in DMF) were added to the reaction vessel. The mixture was allowed to react for 2 min with a microwave potency of 170 V (90°C). The solvents were removed by filtration, and the resin was washed with DMF (3 x 30 s). For Fmoc-His(Trt)-OH, the maximum temperature was reduced to 50°C.

Incorporation of Rhodamine and Maleimide

Before the final cleavage, rhodamine (lissamine rhodamine B sulfonyl chloride) or maleimide (6-maleimidohexanoic acid) was introduced at the *N*-terminus of the peptide. 100 µmol of resin was added to a glass vial in a sand bath at 45°C, and rhodamine (2 equiv.) and DIEA (4 equiv.) in DMF were introduced. The reaction was left to react overnight. Maleimide (4 equiv.), HBTU (4 equiv.) and DIEA (8 equiv.) were added to another 100 µmol of resin and left to react for 2 x 30 min.

Cleavage and Deprotection of Side Chains

After completion of the peptide chain, the resin was washed with DCM (5 x 30 s) and dried by suction for 15 min. The peptides were cleaved from the resin with concomitant removal of the side-chain protecting groups using the following cleavage cocktail: trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), H₂O and triisopropylsilane (TIS) (95:2.5:2.5). After 2h of cleavage, the solvent was evaporated by applying a stream of N₂. The residue was washed 3 times by suspension in *tert*-butyl methyl ether and subsequent centrifugation. Finally, the cleaved peptides were dissolved in H₂O/MeCN (1:1) and lyophilised.

Peptide Purification

Peptides were purified on a Waters system with MassLynx 4.1 software, a 2545 binary gradient module, a 2767 manager collector, a SFO system fluid organiser, a 3100 mass detector, a 2998 photodiode assay detector, and a 515 HPLC pump. A Sunfire C₁₈ column

(150 x 10 mm x 3.5 μm , 100 \AA , Waters) was used, using MeCN (0.1% TFA) and H₂O (0.1% TFA) as solvents and a flow rate of 6.6 mL/min.

Peptide Characterisation

The identity of the peptides synthesised was confirmed by MS-HPLC and LQT-FT MS, while their purity was assessed by HPLC.

HPLC

HPLC chromatograms were obtained on a Waters Alliance 2695 with an automatic injector and a photodiode array detector 2998 Waters (Waters, Milford, MA) using a Sunfire C₁₈ column (100 x 4.6 mm x 5 μm , 100 \AA , Waters) and software EmpowerPro 2. The flow rate was 1 mL/min using MeCN (0.036% TFA) and H₂O (0.045% TFA). 8-min linear gradients were used in all cases.

UPLC

UPLC chromatograms were obtained on an Acquity high class (PDA detector, sample manager FNT and Quaternary solvent manager), using an Acquity BEH C₁₈ (50 x 2 mm x 1.7 μm) column. The flow rate was 0.61 mL/min and MeCN (0.036% TFA) and H₂O (0.045% TFA) were used as solvents. 2-min linear gradients were used in all cases.

MS-HPLC

Chromatograms for all the peptides were recorded on a Waters system Alliance 2695, photodiode detector Waters 2998, ESI-MS model Micromass ZQ and using a MassLynx 4.1 software (Waters, Milford, MA). Using a Sunfire C₁₈ column (100 x 2.1 mm x 3.5 μm , 100 \AA , Waters). The flow rate was 0.3 mL/min, and MeCN (0.07% formic acid) and H₂O (0.1% formic acid) were used as solvents.

LTQ-FT MS

A high-resolution mass spectrometer was used to determine the exact mass of the peptides. The samples were diluted in H₂O/MeCN (1:1) with 1% formic acid and analysed with an LTQ-FT Ultra (Thermo Scientific). They were introduced by automated nanoelectrospray. A NanoMate (Advion BioSciences, Ithaca, NY) infused the samples through the nanoESI Chip (which consisted of 400 nozzles in a 20 x 20 array). The spray voltage was 1.70 kV, and the delivery pressure was 0.5 psi. MS conditions were as follows: Nano-ESI, positive ionisation, capillary temperature 200°C, tube lens 100V, ion spray voltage 2kV, and *m/z* 200–2000 a.m.u.

Amino Acid Analysis

Amino acid analysis was performed to assess the amino acids present and the amount obtained for each peptide. For this purpose, ion exchange chromatographic analysis after acid hydrolysis was performed. The samples were hydrolysed with 6M HCl at 110°C for 16 h. They were then evaporated to dryness at reduced pressure and dissolved in 20 mM of aqueous HCl. Finally, the amino acids were derivatised using the AccQ Tag protocol from Waters, and analysed by ion exchange HPLC.

XTT Cell Proliferation Assay

Cells (bEnd.3 and HeLa) were seeded on 96-well plates (5000 cells/well). After 24 h, the peptide was added at two concentrations (100 and 33.3 µM) to the wells and incubated for another 24 h. The Activated-XTT solution was prepared by adding 0.1 ml of the activation reagent (PMS: *N*-methyl dibenzopyrazine methyl sulphate) to 5 ml of the XTT reagent. 50 µl of this solution was then added to each well and incubated for 4 h. Absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 475 nm using a microtiter plate reader.

Cell viability was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ viability} = 100 - (100 \cdot (A_{max} - A)/(A_{max} - \textit{Blank}))$$

where *A*_{max} is the absorbance of the cells without peptide, *Blank* is the absorbance of the medium alone, and *A* is the absorbance of the sample.

Internalisation Experiments

Cells for the internalisation experiments (bEnd.3) were cultured in DMEM complete medium (glucose 4.5 g/l and 2 mM glutamine) with 10% FBS. The medium was changed 3 times each week, and cell passage was performed with 0.05% trypsin/EDTA. Two days before the experiment, 100000 bEnd.3 cells/well were seeded in 24-well plates. On the day of the assay, the cells were washed with Ringer HEPES for 15 min and then treated for another 15 min with selected inhibitors, namely sodium azide (10 mM), filipin III (10 µg/mL), chlorpromazine hydrochloride (10 µg/mL) or vehicle (Ringer HEPES). After this preincubation, enough rhodamine-labelled peptide or ¹²⁵I-labelled GFP conjugate was added to reach a final concentration of 50 µM or 100 nM, respectively. After 30 min of incubation at 37°C or 4°C, the cells were washed 5 times with Ringer HEPES at 4°C, trypsinised and kept on ice. Cells were immediately analysed using a FACSAria Fusion flow cytometer with a 582 nm laser or a Packard Cobra II Gamma Counter.

Confocal Microscopy

For the experiments in the confocal microscope, the cells (5000 cells/dish) were seeded on collagen pre-coated MatTek glass-bottom culture dishes (MatTek Corporation, Ashland, MA) and incubated for 48 h at 37°C. They were given a complete media change before being treated with Rh-SGV peptide or rhodamine in reduced 1% serum media. After 30 min, cells were washed 3 times with 1 mL media and immediately imaged.

Fluorescence was detected on a Zeiss LSM 780 laser scanning confocal microscope equipped with temperature-controlled environmental chamber and CO₂ for live-cell imaging. Images were taken with a Zeiss Plan-Apochromat 63x/1.40 oil DIC M27 objective. Rhodamine fluorescence was excited with a HeNe laser at 543 nm and emission was detected at 560 nm. AlexaFluor 488 and Hoechst were excited with an argon laser at 488 and 405 nm, and emission was recorded at 546 and 458 nm, respectively. Pinholes were set to equate optical slice thicknesses. The images were processed using the ImageJ 1.49b software.

GFP Modification

2-iminothiolane (15 equiv., 2 mg/mL in H₂O) was added to a solution of GFP (1 mg/mL) in sodium phosphate buffer (NaPi) (50 mM, pH 8, 150 mM NaCl, 1mM EDTA). The reaction proceeded for 1 h at RT, and excess reagent was removed by SEC following the manufacturer's instructions (PDminitrapp, for volumes up to 0.5 mL, PDmiditrap for volumes up to 1 mL or PD10 for volumes up to 2.5 mL, GE Healthcare). The maleimido-peptide (10 equiv.) was added for 1 h at RT to alkylate the activated protein. The resulting protein was purified by SEC. BCA (Piercenet®) was used to determine the total protein concentration. Coomassie-stained SDS-PAGE and Image Studio Software were used to determine the amount of peptide copies that incorporated GFP. The molecular weight of the conjugates was determined by LTQ-FT MS and were: 0 copies [m/z Expected: 27075 Da; Found: 27075 Da], 1 copy [m/z Expected: 28823 Da; Found: 28820 Da] and 2 copies [m/z Expected: 30571; Found: 30567 Da].

¹²⁵I Protein Labelling

Pierce™ Iodination Beads (Life Technologies) were used to radiolabel the protein conjugates. Briefly, two beads per protein were washed with 500 µL of reaction buffer (50 mM NaPi, pH 6.5) and dried on filter paper. In a glass vial, the beads were added with the sufficient amount of carrier-free Na¹²⁵I (1 mCi/mg protein) in 200 µl of reaction buffer. The reaction was incubated for 5 min. The proteins were then added and the reaction was carried out for 15 min with occasional mixing. The reaction was stopped by removing the solution from the reaction vessel and adding it to a NAP-5 column (GE Healthcare) previously equilibrated with PBS. The iodinated protein was dialysed (Slide-A-Lyzer® minidialysis devices, 20K, 0.5 mL) overnight against Ringer HEPES to further remove the unincorporated ¹²⁵I. The radioactivity of 10-µl fractions was measured for 2 min using a Packard Cobra II Gamma Counter, and the protein concentration was determined using BCA analysis (Piercenet®).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phage Display Against a BBB Cellular Model

To perform the panning against the *in vitro* BBB cellular model, the Ph.D.-12™ Phage Display Peptide Library (New England Biolabs, Hitchin, UK) was selected as the starting

phage pool. This library is based on a M13 phage vector, which is modified in the minor coat protein pIII for pentavalent display of peptides as *N*-terminus fusion proteins. This library represents 1.2×10^9 unique peptide sequences with the general motif $N\text{-XXXXXXXXXXXXX-GGGS}^C$, where X_{12} represents a unique 12-mer peptide and GGGS is a short amino acid spacer that links the *C*-terminus of the peptide to the *N*-terminus of the pIII coat protein of the phage. For these experiments, 5×10^{10} pfu of the phage display peptide library was added to the donor compartment and incubated for 2 h (Figure 1). After this time, the acceptor and donor compartments were recovered. The phage from the former was amplified in *E. coli* and used as the initial pool for the second round of panning. This cycle was carried out a second time, and the DNA of 34 individual phage was sequenced. Also, as an internal control of barrier integrity, Lucifer Yellow was added to the well with the phage library. The permeability (Papp) values of this molecule was around $12 \cdot 10^{-6}$ cm/s – a value below the acceptable maximum limit of $15 \cdot 10^{-6}$ cm/s.

A broad range of peptide sequences were obtained from the recovered phage, the following sequences being repeated more than once: QTFSRPDWTMYL (2/34); SGVYKVAYDWQH (5/34); and SSLELSRSSAAS (2/34). As little consensus was obtained, the biopanning experiment was repeated a second time, using the unbiased library as the starting phage pool and repeating the biopanning cycle three times. On this second occasion, 31 phage particles were sequenced, and the translocation of the sequence SGVYKVAYDWQH (2/31) was again found to be favoured (Table II).

The BBB cellular model is formed by endothelial cells that present hundreds of different receptors capable of pulling a specific ligand out of the library and translocating the phage to the acceptor compartment. This diversity can yield a complex mixture of peptides with no clear consensus, as seen before.²⁷ The results of these two independent experiments revealed this tendency but also a sequence repeated in both experiments and more than once (SGVYKVAYDWQH). We therefore selected this peptide as a candidate for a new BBB-shuttle.

Synthesis and Validation of the Selected Candidate

To validate the capacity of SGV (H-SGVYKVAYDWQH-NH₂) as a BBB-shuttle, it was synthesised using standard Fmoc/*t*Bu solid-phase peptide synthesis³⁵ on an automatic peptide synthesiser (Liberty Blue synthesiser, CEM). The Rink Amide ChemMatrix resin

was used to provide an amide at the *C*-terminus of the peptide to avoid the presence of a free negatively charged carboxylate, as the peptide was fused through this part to the phage and did not present this charge.

Several versions of the peptide were synthesised (Table III): the naked peptide, to be used in toxicity assays and the validation in the BBB cellular model (SGV); with a rhodamine at the *N*-terminus, to be used in the study of the internalisation mechanism (Rh-SGV); and with a maleimide at the *N*-terminus, to be used in the conjugation to a model cargo (Mal-SGV).

An XTT cell proliferation assay was performed to ensure that SGV presented low toxicity. In this regard, the peptide was incubated at two concentrations (100 and 33.3 μM) with bEnd.3 and HeLa cells for 24 h. Cell viability was assessed after the addition of the XTT reagent for 4 h. As predicted, this peptide had low toxicity, as reflected by cell viability above 90% at both concentrations.

The permeability of SGV was assessed using the *in vitro* BBB cellular model. The peptide was added to the donor compartment (apical) at 50 μM , and its recovery in the acceptor compartment (basal) was quantified by UPLC. The permeability obtained was $(4.4 \pm 0.6) \cdot 10^{-6}$ cm/s. When performing the assay at 4°C, the permeability was reduced by 40%, implying that the peptide internalised through an active mechanism. In another experiment, the peptide was added to the basal compartment and the amount transported to the apical compartment was also reduced by 40%. These results provide the first indication that SGV transport may be receptor-mediated (Figure 2A).

Transport Mechanism of SGV peptide

To gain further insight into the internalisation mechanism of SGV, we performed internalisation assays in bEnd.3 cells.³⁶ This is an immortalised mouse brain endothelial cell line that displays similar characteristics to the BBB. For these experiments, SGV was synthesised with the rhodamine fluorescent dye at the *N*-terminus. This fluorophore gives red fluorescence and is widely used for labelling peptides.³⁷

The internalisation experiments were performed by incubating the rhodamine-labelled peptide (Rh-SGV) with bEnd.3 cells for 30 min and then evaluating peptide uptake using

flow cytometry. Selected inhibitors were added for 15 min prior to the incorporation of the peptide in order to gather information on the mechanism of endocytosis (Figure 2B).

To test whether the internalisation of SGV is through an active mechanism, bEnd.3 cells were incubated with sodium azide to reduce ATP production or kept at 4°C during the experiment to reduce cell metabolism. Both sodium azide (uptake of 57% with respect to Rh-SGV) and temperature (17%) affected endocytosis, thereby suggesting an active uptake mechanism. We then added chlorpromazine, a cationic amphipathic drug that inhibits clathrin-mediated endocytosis of various plasma membrane proteins, and fillipin III, a polyene antibiotic involved in the inhibition of caveolae-mediated endocytosis, to the cells prior to the peptide. On this occasion, only chlorpromazine (70%) produced a decrease in Rh-SGV uptake, thereby implying the involvement of a clathrin-mediated mechanism.

Moreover, the internalisation of SGV in two cell lines (bEnd.3 cells and human endothelial cells used in the *in vitro* BBB cellular model) was confirmed by confocal microscopy. The rhodamine-labelled peptide was incubated with the cells on MatTek plates and imaged after 30 min. AlexaFluor 488-labeled transferrin (AF-Tf) was used as a marker for early endosomes and Hoechst for cell nuclei. Rh-SGV co-localised with AF-Tf (Figure 3) while rhodamine alone did not enter the cells (data not shown). All this data confirms that SGV internalises both in murine and human endothelial cells. Also, this evidence, together with the inhibition by chlorpromazine, suggests that the internalisation mechanism involved in SGV uptake is clathrin-mediated, as Tf internalises also by this mechanism. Given that this endocytic mechanism is used by most receptors of the BBB, such as the receptors of transferrin, epidermal growth factor, and low-density lipoprotein, SGV emerges as a potentially useful BBB-shuttle.³⁸

Ability to Improve Cargo Uptake

For a peptide to be considered a BBB-shuttle, it must be able to improve the permeability of a cargo that is not able to enter the brain unaided. In this regard, the capacity of SGV to improve the internalisation of Green Fluorescent Protein (GFP) in bEnd.3 cells was evaluated.³⁹ GFP is used as a model protein for others that would be interesting to deliver to the brain for protein replacement therapy, such as Frataxin⁴⁰ or α -N-acetylglucosaminidase (NAGLU).⁴¹

SGV was covalently attached to GFP in the following way (Figure 4A). First, GFP was modified with 2-iminothiolane to incorporate a thiol at the lysine residues. The maleimido-version of the peptide then reacted with this free thiol to form a stable thioether. With this reaction, up to three copies of the peptide can be introduced into the protein. In this case, the reaction of GFP with Mal-SGV yielded 43% as unreacted protein, 43% incorporating one copy of the peptide and 14% with two copies (Figure 4B).

To perform the internalisation experiments, the conjugates were labelled with ^{125}I , and uptake was measured using a gamma counter. Radioactive labelling was used to detect the protein at the concentration of the assay (100 nM). Using this low concentration, macromolecular effects are reduced and the conditions are more similar to those used *in vivo*. The uptake of GFP (632 ± 43 fmol GFP/mg protein) increased 2-fold when conjugated to SGV (1374 ± 145 fmol GFP/mg protein) (Figure 2C). Also, by lowering the temperature to 4°C, the uptake of GFP-SGV remained at the same levels as GFP alone (731 ± 108 fmol GFP/mg protein). These observations indicate that SGV also facilitates the internalisation of GFP in bEnd.3 cells, thereby opening the door to the transport of other cargoes, including proteins for protein replacement therapy.

CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated that phage display can be applied to a BBB cellular model to identify peptide sequences that translocate across the BBB. Using this approach, we found the SGV sequence from a 12-mer library, which has a moderate to high permeability in the BBB cellular model. We have also shown that this peptide is able to enter endothelial cells, probably through clathrin-mediated endocytosis, and that it also improves the uptake of GFP. But more importantly, we have shown the usefulness of the human *in vitro* BBB model for the discovery of new BBB-shuttles.

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REFERENCES

- ¹ Pardridge, W. M. *NeuroRx* 2005, 2, 3-14.
- ² Pardridge, W. M. *Drug Discovery Today* 2007, 12, 54-61.
- ³ Pardridge, W. M. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab* 2012, 32, 1959-1972.
- ⁴ Boer, A. G. de; Gaillard, P. J *Annu Rev Pharmacol Toxicol* 2007, 47, 323-355.
- ⁵ Malakoutikhah, M.; Teixidó, M.; Giralt, E. *Angew Chem Int Ed* 2011, 50, 7998-8014.
- ⁶ Visser, C. C.; Stevanovic, S.; Voorwiden, L. H.; van Bloois, L.; Gaillard, P. J.; Danhof, M.; Crommelin, D. J.; de Boer, A. G. *Eur J Pharm Sci* 2005, 25, 299-305.
- ⁷ Oller-Salvia, B.; Sánchez-Navarro, M.; Giralt, E.; Teixidó, M. *Chem Soc Rev* 2016, DOI. 10.1039/c6cs00076b.
- ⁸ Pardridge, W. M. *Curr Opin Pharmacol* 2006, 6, 494-500.
- ⁹ Spencer, B. J.; Verma, I. M. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2007, 104, 7594-7599.
- ¹⁰ Demeule, M.; Régina, A.; Ché, C.; Poirier, J.; Nguyen, T.; Gabathuler, R.; Castaigne, J.-P.; Béliveau, R. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther* 2008, 324, 1064-1072.
- ¹¹ Demeule, M.; Currie, J. C.; Bertrand, Y.; Ché, C.; Nguyen, T.; Régina, A.; Gabathuler, R.; Castaigne, J. P.; Béliveau, R. *J Neurochem* 2008, 106, 1534-1544.
- ¹² Ke, W.; Shao, K.; Huang, R.; Han, L.; Liu, Y.; Li, J.; Kuang, Y.; Ye, L.; Lou, J.; Jiang, C. *Biomaterials* 2009, 30, 6976-6985.
- ¹³ Wang, D.; El-Amouri, S. S.; Dai, M.; Kuan, C.-Y.; Hui, D. Y.; Brady, R. O.; Pan, D. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2013, 110, 2999-3004.
- ¹⁴ Lam, K. S.; Lebl, M.; Krchňák, V. *Chem Rev* 1997, 97, 411-448.
- ¹⁵ Guixer, B.; Arroyo, X.; Belda, I.; Sabidó, E.; Teixidó, M.; Giralt, E. *J Pept Sci* 2016, *in press*.
- ¹⁶ Smith, G.P.; Petrenko, V.A. *Chem Rev* 1997, 97, 391-410.
- ¹⁷ Smith, G.P. *Science* 1985, 228, 1315-1317.
- ¹⁸ Hamzeh-Mivehroud, M.; Alizadeh, A. A.; Morris, M. B.; Bret Church, W.; Dastmalchi, S. *Drug Discovery Today* 2013, 18, 1144-1157.
- ¹⁹ Georgieva, J. V.; Brinkhuis, R. P.; Stojanov, K.; Weijers, C. A. G. M.; Zuilhof, H.; Rutjes, F. P. J. T.; Hoekstra, D.; Van Hest, J. C. M.; Zuhorn, I. S. *Angew Chem Int Ed* 2012, 51, 8339-8342.
- ²⁰ Xia, H.; Anderson, B.; Mao, Q.; Beverly, L. *J Virol* 2000, 74, 11359-11366.
- ²¹ Malcor, J. D.; Payrot, N.; David, M.; Faucon, A.; Abouzid, K.; Jacquot, G.; Floquet, N.; Debarbieux, F.; Rougon, G.; Martinez, J.; Khrestchatisky, M.; Vlieghe, P.; Lisowski, V. *J Med Chem* 2012, 55, 2227-2241.
- ²² Pasqualini R.; Ruoslahti, E. *Nature* 1996, 380, 364-366.
- ²³ Bakhshinejad, B.; Karimi, M.; Khalaj-Kondori, M. *Neural Regener Res* 2015, 10, 862-865.
- ²⁴ Li, J.; Feng, L.; Fan, L.; Zha, Y.; Guo, L.; Zhang, Q.; Chen, J.; Pang, Z.; Wang, Y.; Jiang, X.; Yang, V.C.; Wen, L. *Biomaterials* 2011, 32, 4943-4950.
- ²⁵ Staquicini, F. I.; Ozawa, M. G.; Moya, C. A.; Driessen, W. H. P.; Barbu, E. M.; Nishimori, H.; Soghomonyan, S.; Flores, L. G.; Liang, X.; Paolillo, V.; Alauddin, M. M.; Babilion, J. P.; Furnari, F. B.; Bogler, O.; Lang, F. F.; Aldape, K. D.; Fuller, G. N.; Höök, M.; Gelovani, J. G.; Sidman, R. L.; Cavenee, W. K.; Pasqualini, R.; Arap, W. *J Clin Invest* 2011, 121, 161-173.
- ²⁶ Li, J.; Zhang, Q.; Pang, Z.; Wang, Y.; Liu, Q.; Guo, L.; Jiang, X. *Amino Acids* 2012, 42, 2373-2381.
- ²⁷ Van Rooy, I.; Cakir-Tascioglu, S.; Couraud, P. O.; Romero, I. A.; Weksler, B.; Storm, G.; Hennink, W. E.; Schiffelers, R. M.; Mastrobattista, E. *Pharm Res* 2010, 27, 673-682.
- ²⁸ Smith, M. W.; Al-Jayyousi, G.; Gumbleton, M. *Peptides* 2012, 38, 172-180.

- ²⁹ Lee, J. H.; Engler, J. A.; Collawn, J. F.; Moore, B. A. *Eur J Biochem* 2001, 268, 2004-2012.
- ³⁰ Bicker, J.; Alves, G.; Fortuna, A.; Falcão, A. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 2014, 87, 409-432.
- ³¹ Cecchelli, R.; Aday, S.; Sevin, E.; Almeida, C.; Culot, M.; Dehouck, L.; Coisne, C.; Engelhardt, B.; Dehouck, M. P.; Ferreira, L. *PLoS One* 2014, 9, e99733.
- ³² Prades, R.; Oller-Salvia, B.; Schwarzmaier, S. M.; Selva, J.; Moros, M.; Balbi, M.; Grazú, V.; De La Fuente, J. M.; Egea, G.; Plesnila, N.; Teixidó, M.; Giralt, E. *Angew Chem Int Ed* 2015, 54, 3967-3972.
- ³³ Oller-Salvia, B.; Sánchez-Navarro, M.; Ciudad, S.; Guiu, M.; Arranz-Gibert, P.; Garcia, C.; Gomis, R. R.; Cecchelli, R.; García, J.; Giralt, E.; Teixidó, M. *Angew Chem Int Ed* 2016, 55, 572-575.
- ³⁴ Kaiser, E.; Colescott, R. L.; Bossinger, C. D.; Cook, P. I. *Anal Biochem* 1970, 34, 595-598.
- ³⁵ Merrifield, B. *Peptides: Synthesis, Structures and Applications*; Academic Press, Inc.: San Diego, 1995.
- ³⁶ Brown, R. C.; Morris, A. P.; O'Neil, R. G. *Brain Res* 2007, 1130, 17-30.
- ³⁷ Moreno, M.; Zurita, E.; Giralt, E. *J Control Release* 2014, 182, 13-21.
- ³⁸ McMahon, H. T.; Boucrot, E. *Nature Rev* 2011, 12, 517-533.
- ³⁹ Tsien, R. Y. *Annu Rev Biochem* 1998, 67, 509-544.
- ⁴⁰ Campuzano, V.; Montermini, L.; Lutz, Y.; Cova, L.; Hindelang, C.; Jiralerspong, S.; Trottier, Y.; Kish, S. J.; Faucheux, B.; Trouillas, P.; Authier, F. J.; Dürr, A.; Mandel, J. L.; Vescovi, A.; Pandolfo, M.; Koenig, M. *Hum Mol Genet* 1997, 6, 1771-1780.
- ⁴¹ Desnick, R. J.; Schuchman, E. H. *Annu Rev Genom Hum Genet* 2012, 13, 307-335.

TABLES AND FIGURES

Table I BBB-Peptide Shuttles Discovered by Phage Display

Table II Sequences of Individual Phage Clones Recovered After Panning

Table III Molecular Weight, Purity and Yield of the Peptides Synthesized

FIGURE 1 Schematic representation of the biopanning of a phage display library against a human BBB cellular model. (a) Addition of the phage library to the human BBB cellular model, (b) incubation for 2 h, (c) recovery and amplification of the acceptor compartment, (d) repetition 2-4 times, and (e) phage isolation and DNA sequencing.

FIGURE 2 A) Permeability relative to the SGV peptide in the *in vitro* BBB cellular model. B) Effect of selective inhibitors on the uptake of Rh-SGV by bEnd.3 cells, as analysed by FACS. C) Differences in the uptake of GFP conjugated to the SGV peptide in bEnd.3. All values are reported as the Mean \pm SEM (n=2-8, ****p<0.0001, ***p<0.001, **p<0.01; t-test).

FIGURE 3 Confocal fluorescent microscopy of endothelial cells after 30 min of co-incubation at 37°C with Rh-SGV and AF-Tf. Rh-SGV is shown in red, AF-Tf in green, cell nuclei (Hoechst staining) in blue, and co-localisation in yellow. The scale bar represents 15 μ m.

FIGURE 4 A) Scheme of the conjugation of Mal-SGV to GFP and B) characterisation of GFP-SGV conjugate with Coomassie-stained SDS-PAGE.

Table I

Peptide	Sequence	Biopanning method	Phage library	Ref
B6	G-GHKAKGPRK-LGS	Screening against the purified extracellular domain of hTfR	Custom 9-mer peptide phage library	20
Peptide-22	Ac-C(&)MPRLRGC(&)-NH ₂	Biopanning directed to the extracellular domain of the human low density lipoprotein receptor (LDLR)	Random cyclic 15-mer peptide phage library	21
0G23	HLNILSTLWKYRC	Selection on immobilised monosialotetrahexosylganglioside (GM1)	Ph.D.-12 phage display peptide library (from New England Biolabs)	19
THR HAI	THRPPMWSVPWP HAIYPRH	Alternating rounds of negative selection on chicken embryo fibroblast cells lacking hTfR (CEF) and positive selection on chicken embryo fibroblast cells expressing hTfR (CEF+hTfR)	Ph.D.-12 and Ph.D.-7 phage display peptide library (from New England Biolabs)	29
-SxTSSTx-	AC-SYTSSTM-CGGGS	Intravascular administration in rats and separate harvesting of brain microvascular capillaries and brain parenchyma after vascular surface washing	Ph.D.-C7C phage display peptide library (from New England Biolabs)	28
CRT	CRTIGPSVC	Administration of the phage library i.v. to normal mice and recovery of the enriched population of brain-homing phage after 3 selection rounds	Random cyclic 7-mer peptide phage library	25
PepC7	CTSTSAPYC	Phages were recovered from mouse brain parenchyma after i.v. administration	Ph.D.-C7C phage display peptide library (from New England Biolabs)	26
TGN	TGNYKALHPHNG	Mice were injected in the tail vein with the phage and after a period of circulation, the blood was collected and the brain was removed	Ph.D.-12 phage display peptide library (from New England Biolabs)	24
GLA GYR	GLAHSFSDFARDFVA GYRPVHNIRGHWAPG	Screening was performed by perfusion via the heart of a phage library through the murine brain <i>in situ</i>	Random 15-mer peptide phage library	27

Table II

Biopanning 1			Biopanning 2		
Phage clone	Sequence	Frequency	Phage clone	Sequence	Frequency
1.1	DPDDTHIMRLLY	1/34	2.1	KLNSLDSGMRLV	1/31
1.2	XKSTASMFTTAR	1/34	2.2	AFNPSTPHLRLI	1/31
1.3	GSAARWPFSVTL	1/34	2.3	GLTGDLSLNTAT	1/31
1.4	LTNTSQLQTRIG	1/34	2.4	ETLSSYVKKPGH	1/31
1.5	QTFSRPDWTMYL	2/34	2.5	SGVYKVAYDWQH	2/31
1.6	QTFSRPDWTMYL	2/34	2.6	AIYMDTGPLAGR	1/31
1.7	SQDIRTWNGTRS	1/34	2.7	SLPVGSSSDGWV	1/31
1.8	IEINATRAGTNL	1/34	2.8	LPLSYNDKARAE	1/31
1.9	SGVYKVAYDWQH	5/34	2.9	RVSIESHHLHDHY	1/31
1.10	SMRASYPMPFTI	1/34	2.10	DGAVSYLQLRVT	1/31
1.11	GLHTSATNLYLH	1/34	2.11	GLHTSATNLYLH	1/31
1.12	FPGLFEMVESLN	1/34	2.12	FIPFDPMSMRWE	1/31
1.13	VNMVPLGKNVVQ	1/34	2.13	LDQLPCCWSKTG	1/31
1.14	IDAHFGLRLVND	1/34	2.14	WVNDTNSPLVPR	1/31
1.15	GSGASYQVWRPM	1/34	2.15	MLAPRQTEHGRI	1/31
1.16	SGVYKVAYDWQH	5/34	2.16	LMKSPQLHSSR	1/31
1.17	MHYGTYTVGYKQ	1/34	2.17	MHPNAGHGSLMR	1/31
1.18	VLKEASHLPYSG	1/34	2.18	GQAPSVPFFASI	1/31
1.19	SGVYKVAYDWQH	5/34	2.19	NERNHEIMMAQA	1/31
1.20	GDYGDGFRLLYI	1/34	2.20	SGVYKVAYDWQH	2/31
1.21	VAGLKEQAELDY	1/34	2.21	HEMYSSFGALTV	1/31
1.22	TSWNMGLTYAGQ	1/34	2.22	NMANYSAISSRW	1/31
1.23	VLTNIARGEYMR	1/34	2.23	STPIFAEATARS	1/31
1.24	SSLELSRSSAAS	2/34	2.24	HSADINVGSRTR	1/31
1.25	GQAGGEWILHPL	1/34	2.25	DEAAYGLKLPKG	1/31
1.26	SSLELSRSSAAS	2/34	2.26	DLGRASSILPSG	1/31
1.27	SGVYKVAYDWQH	5/34	2.27	GLFGNEARTAST	1/31
1.28	AASSGVTVTLPT	1/34	2.28	YTNDHSRPKLVP	1/31
1.29	GESVSRIDVGSA	1/34	2.29	SVNSDHTSMRSH	1/31
1.30	TTVTGASFSAAY	1/34	2.30	AVMPRDHVLNAT	1/31
1.31	IEASFYDAPRGG	1/34	2.31	LHRQDNYLAASX	1/31
1.32	KASGSPSGFWPS	1/34			
1.33	GSWGLNDSHSYR	1/34			
1.34	SGVYKVAYDWQH	5/34			

Phage-displayed selected sequence is shown in bold.

Table III

Peptide	Molecular formula	Calc Mw, Da	Found Mw, Da ^a	t _R HPLC, min ^b	Purity, % ^b	Yield, % ^c
SGV	C ₆₈ H ₉₄ O ₁₈ N ₁₈	1450.6988	1450.6986	4.3	>95	8
Rh-SGV	C ₉₅ H ₁₂₂ O ₂₄ N ₂₀ S ₂	1990.8382	1990.8381	5.3	>95	5
Mal-SGV	C ₇₈ H ₁₀₅ O ₂₁ N ₁₉	1643.7727	1643.7725	4.9	>95	6

^a Calculated by LQT-FT MS.

^b Calculated by HPLC.

^c Calculated by amino acid analysis.

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

TOC

The discovery of new BBB-shuttle, to improve the transport of therapeutic drugs into the brain, is a major challenge. Here we report on the use of phage display against a human BBB cellular model, to identify peptide sequences that translocate across the BBB. Internalisation studies in endothelial cells with the selected peptide, demonstrate that this peptide probably internalises through a clathrin-mediated mechanism and that it is also able to increase the uptake of a cargo.